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Research Article

Method Development and Validation for The Simultaneous Estimation of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms by RP-HPLC

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ABSTRACT

A simple, accurate and precise High Performance Liquid Chromatographic (HPLC) method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride in bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage form. Chromatogram was run through Inertsil – C18, ODS column, 150 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ . Mobile phase containing Methanol:Acetonitrile taken in the ratio 70:30 was pumped through column at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Optimized wavelength selected was 289 nm. Retention time of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was found to be 4.713 min and 6.691 min. The % RSD for Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was 0.042 and 0.057. % Recovery was obtained as 100.16% and 100.29% for Pioglitazone and Glimepiride respectively. Obtained LOD, LOQ values of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride were 0.070, 0.212 and 0.096, 0.293 μ g/ml respectively. Linearity range was 20 – 80 μ g/ml for both the drugs. Regression equation of Pioglitazone was $y=9884.3x-380.39$ and that of Glimepiride is $y=56481x-2387.5$ Results show that the retention and run time were decreased, so it is evident that the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

INTRODUCTION

Pioglitazone belongs to the class Thiazolidinediones. Pioglitazone is an antihyperglycemic used as an adjunct to diet, exercise, and other antidiabetic medications to manage type 2 diabetes mellitus. Pioglitazone is a selective agonist at peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-gamma (PPAR γ) in target

tissues for insulin action such as adipose tissue, skeletal muscle, and liver. Activation of PPAR γ increases the transcription of insulin-responsive genes involved in the control of glucose and lipid production, transport, and utilization. Through this mechanism, pioglitazone both enhances tissue sensitivity to insulin and reduces the hepatic production of glucose (i.e. gluconeogenesis) -

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insulin resistance associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus is therefore improved without an increase in insulin secretion by pancreatic beta cells.

Glimepiride is a member of the second-generation sulfonylurea (SU) drug class used for the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) to improve glycemic control. Glimepiride blocks the ATP-sensitive potassium channel by binding non-specifically to the B sites of both sulfonylurea receptor-1 (SUR1) and sulfonylurea receptor-2A (SUR2A) subunits as well as the A site of SUR1 subunit of the channel to promote insulin secretion from the beta cell.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- **Materials:** Pioglitazone, Glimepiride, combination of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride, HPLC grade Methanol, acetonitrile, water.
- **Instrument:** HPLC instrument used was of WATERS HPLC SYSTEM 2690/5 with Auto Injector and PDA Detector. Software used is Empower 2. UVVIS spectrophotometer PG Instruments T60 with special bandwidth of 2mm and 10mm and matched quartz was be used for measuring absorbance for Pioglitazone and Glimepiride solutions.
- **Preparation of solutions:**

Preparation of a stock solution: 100 mg of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride each were weighed accurately and dissolved separately in 100 ml volumetric flasks, sonicated for 20 min to obtain 1000g/ml of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride respectively.

Preparation of sample stock solution: Twenty tablets were weighed and the average weight of each tablet was calculated, and a quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 100 mg of Pioglitazone and 100mg Glimepiride were weighed and dissolved in 100 ml of diluent with the aid of ultra sonication for 20 min to furnish a sample stock solution.

Preparation of working standard solution: From the above standard stock solution 4 ml from each solution was taken into a 100 ml volumetric

flask then made up the volume with diluents and sonicated for 10 min and filtered through 0.45µm membrane filter.

Preparation of sample working solution: The sample stock solution was filtered through a 0.45 µm nylon syringe filter and 4 ml of the filtrate was diluted into 100 ml volumetric flask to give a sample solution containing 40µg/ml Pioglitazone and 40µg/ml Glimepiride.

Method Validation:

System suitability parameters: The system suitability parameters were determined by preparing standard solutions of Pioglitazone (40ppm) and Glimepiride (40ppm) and the solutions were injected six times and the parameters like peak tailing, resolution and USP plate count were determined. The % RSD for the area of six standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

Specificity: Specificity is checking of the interference in the optimized method. We should not find interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So this method was said to be specific.

Linearity: Linearity for the drugs Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was determined by preparing the standard solutions at seven concentrations levels in six replicates in the range of 20-80µg/ml for Pioglitazone and 20-80µg/ml for Glimepiride from stock solution.

Accuracy: Accuracy was performed by spiking known amounts of standard solution to sample solution at three different concentrations levels (50%, 100%, 150%). % recovery should be between 98-102%.

Precision: The precision of the analytical method was studied by injecting six replicates of standard containing 40µg/ml of Pioglitazone and 40µg/ml of Glimepiride which were injected into HPLC system. The % RSD should not be more than 2.0%

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ):

The limit of detection was defined as the concentration which yields a signal - to - noise ratio 3:1 where as the limit of quantification was calculated to be the lowest concentration that could be measured with signal - to - noise ratio 10:1. LOD and LOQ were calculated from slope and standard deviation.

Robustness: The smallest deliberate changes in method like change in flow rate are made but there were no predictable changes in the results and are in the range as per ICH guidelines. Conditions like flow rate minus (0.8 ml/min), flow rate plus (1.2 ml/min) was maintained and sample were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters should not be much affected.

Assay: Assay was conducted on marketed formulation and mean % assay was found.

Optimized wavelength selected was 289nm.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT:

Method development was done by changing various, mobile phase ratios, buffers etc.

Trial - 1 Chromatographic conditions:

Flow rate : 1.0ml / min
 Column : Inertsil-C18, ODS
 Mobile Phase : Degassed Acetonitrile : Water (90:10) .
 Detector Wave length : 289nm
 Injection Volume : 20µl
 Run time : 6 min
 Retention time : 3.156 min for Pioglitazone and 4.417 min for Glimperide
 Result : Tailing and fronting was observed for both the drugs. So next trail was performed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1: Chromatogram of trial 1

Trial -2 Chromatographic conditions

Mobile phase : Water: Methanol (45:55)
 Flow rate : 1.0ml / min
 Column : Inertsil-C18, ODS
 Wave length : 289nm
 Injection volume : 20µl

Run Time : 6 min
 Retention time : 2.838 min for Pioglitazone and 3.602 min for Glimperide.
 Result : The drug peaks were merged and tailing was observed. So next trail was performed.

Fig. 2: Chromatogram of trial 2

Trial – 3 Chromatographic conditions

Flow rate	: 1.0ml / min	Injection volume	: 20µl
Column	: Inertsil-C18, ODS	Run Time	: 6 min
Detector wave length	: 289nm	Retention time	: 2.902 min for Pioglitazone and 3.618 min for Glimepiride.
Mobile phase (10:90)	: Acetonitrile: Methanol	Result	: The two peaks were merged and tailing was observed. So, next trial was performed

Fig. 3: Chromatogram for trail 3

Optimized chromatographic Conditions

Parameters	Method
Stationary phase (column)	Inertsil -ODS C ₁₈ (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 µ)
Mobile Phase	Methanol :Acetonitrile (70:30)
Flow rate (ml/min)	1.0 ml/min
Run time (minutes)	12 min
Column temperature (°C)	Ambient
Volume of injection loop (µl)	20
Detection wavelength (nm)	289 nm
Drug RT (min)	4.713 min for Pioglitazone and 6.691 for Glimepiride.

Fig. 4: Optimized Chromatogram

Observation: Pioglitazone and Glimepiride were eluted at 4.713 min and 6.691 min respectively with good resolution. Plate count and tailing factor

was very satisfactory, so this method was optimized and to be validated.

METHOD VALIDATION

1. System Suitability

Fig. 5: System Suitability Chromatogram

Table 1: System Suitability data of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride

S. No	Pioglitazone				Glimepiride			
	RT (min)	Peak area	USP plate count	Tailing	RT (min)	Peak area	USP plate count	Tailing
1	4.707	395655	7523.845	1.056	6.684	2268456	8325.874	1.056
2	4.706	395405	7510.547	1.031	6.681	2264844	8384.547	1.078
3	4.707	395709	7536.874	1.055	6.680	2265855	8314.875	1.058
4	4.708	395851	7527.254	1.079	6.684	2265850	8372.784	1.055
5	4.708	395505	7584.658	1.063	6.682	2265032	8392.084	1.088

Discussion: The % RSD for peak areas of standard solutions of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was 0.053 and 0.073 respectively. The number of theoretical plates for standard solutions of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was 7537 and 8359

respectively. The Tailing factor for the standard solutions of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was 1.063 and 1.060 respectively.

2. Specificity

Fig. 6: Chromatogram of Blank

Fig. 7: Chromatogram of Standard

Discussion: Retention times of Pioglitazone and glimepiride were 4.708 and 6.682 min respectively. We did not find any interfering peaks

at the retention time of these drugs. So this method was found to be specific.

3. Precision:

(a) System Precision

Fig. 8: System Precision Chromatogram

Table 2: System precision Data of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride

S. No	Peak areas of Pioglitazone	Peak areas of Glimepiride
1	395480	2264550
2	395846	2266641
3	395445	2265568
4	395560	2267064
5	395609	2264874
Mean	395551	2266091
SD	167.472	1301.467
% RSD	0.042	0.057

Inference: The % RSD for System Precision of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was 0.042 and 0.057 respectively.

(b) Method precision:

Fig. 9: Method precision chromatogram

Table 3: Method Precision data of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride

S. No	Peak areas of Pioglitazone	Peak areas of Glimepiride
1	395421	2264848
2	395748	2263398
3	395864	2265848
4	395660	2264588
5	395508	2265650

6	395285	2266875
Mean	395581	2265201
SD	215.760	1195.804
% RSD	0.054	0.052

Discussion: The % RSD for Method Precision of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was 0.054 and 0.052 respectively.

4. Accuracy (Recovery):

Fig. 10: Chromatogram of Accuracy-50%

Fig. 11: Chromatogram of Accuracy-100%

Fig. 12: Chromatogram of Accuracy-150%

Table 4: Accuracy Data of Pioglitazone

Concentration % of spiked level	Amount added (ppm)	Amount found (ppm)	% Recovery	Statistical Analysis of % Recovery	
50% - 1	20	20.05	100.27	MEAN	100.18
50% - 2	20	20.03	100.17		

50% - 3	20	20.01	100.08	%RSD	0.096
100 %- 1	40	40.07	100.19	MEAN	100.15
100 %- 2	40	40.05	100.12		
100% - 3	40	40.06	100.15	%RSD	0.034
150% - 1	60	60.08	100.13	MEAN	100.17
150% - 2	60	60.10	100.17		
150% - 3	60	60.12	100.20	%RSD	0.034

Table 5: Accuracy Data for Glimepiride

Concentration % of spiked level	Amount added (ppm)	Amount found (ppm)	% Recovery	Statistical Analysis of % Recovery	
				MEAN	%RSD
50% - 1	20	20.05	100.28	MEAN	100.31
50% - 2	20	20.06	100.32	%RSD	0.030
50% - 3	20	20.06	100.34		
100 % - 1	40	40.15	100.38	MEAN	100.41
100 % - 2	40	40.21	100.58		
100% - 3	40	40.13	100.33	%RSD	0.104
150% - 1	60	60.09	100.15	MEAN	100.17
150% - 2	60	60.10	100.18		
150% - 3	60	60.10	100.18	%RSD	0.017

Discussion: Mean % Recovery of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was 100.16% and 100.29 % respectively.

5. Linearity:

Table 6: Linearity data of Pioglitazone

Concentration (ppm)	Average Area	Statistical Analysis	
0	0	Slope	9884.3
20	197821	y-Intercept	-380.46
30	296731	Correlation Coefficient	0.9999
40	395642		
50	489132		
60	593463		
70	692373		
80	791284		

Fig. 13: Calibration curve of Pioglitazone

Table 7: Linearity data of Glimepiride

Concentration (ppm)	Average area	Statistical Analysis	
0	0	Slope	56481
20	1130470	y-Intercept	-2387.5
30	1695705	Correlation Coefficient	0.9999
40	2260940		
50	2792153		
60	3391410		
70	3956645		
80	4521880		

Fig. 14: Calibration curve of Glimepiride

Discussion: The linearity equations obtained for Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was $y=9884.3x-380.46$ and $y=56481x-2387.5$. The Correlation coefficient (R^2) obtained was 0.9999 for both the drugs.

6. Robustness:

Fig. 15: Chromatogram of flow rate of 0.8ml/min

Fig. 16: Chromatogram of flow rate of 1.0ml/min

Fig. 17: Chromatogram of flow rate of 1.2ml/min

Table 8: Robustness data of Pioglitazone with change in flow rate

Flow 0.8 ml	Std Area	Tailing factor	Flow 1.0 ml	Std Area	Tailing factor	Flow 1.2 ml	Std Area	Tailing factor
	392654	1.086		395487	1.045		398598	1.084
	392586	1.058		395562	1.065		398501	1.059
	392601	1.046		395680	1.024		398764	1.036
	392460	1.095		395709	1.086		398364	1.012
	392699	1.084		395486	1.048		398840	1.045
Avg	392798	1.036	Avg	395846	1.056	Avg	398690	1.066
SD	392633	1.067	SD	395628	1.054	SD	398626	1.050
%RSD	----	0.024	SD	----	0.020	SD	----	0.025

Table 9: Robustness data of Glimepiride with change in flow rate

Flow 0.8 ml	Std Area	Tailing factor	Flow 1.0 ml	Std Area	Tailing factor	Flow 1.2 ml	Std Area	Tailing factor
	2247888	1.008		2264858	1.059		2304875	1.010
	2246878	1.045		2265854	1.086		2305689	1.076
	2247887	1.068		2268565	1.055		2306987	1.093
	2246980	1.080		2266458	1.023		2303671	1.101
	2243698	1.019		2265168	1.074		2306545	1.052
Avg	2245852	1.039	Avg	2266912	1.067	Avg	2307584	1.039
SD	2246530	1.043	SD	2266302	1.060	SD	2305891	1.061
%RSD	---	0.027	%RSD	---	0.021	%RSD	---	0.034

Discussion: The tailing factor for change in flow rate for Pioglitazone and Glimepiride was 0.023 and 0.027 respectively.

7. Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantitation:

Table 10: Sensitivity data of Pioglitazone and Glimepiride

Molecule	LOD (µg/ml)	LOQ (µg/ml)
Pioglitazone	0.070	0.212
Glimepiride	0.096	0.293

8. Assay:

Fig. 18: Assay chromatogram of Pioglitazone and Glimperide

Table 11: Assay data of Pioglitazone and Glimperide

S. No	Pioglitazone		Glimperide	
1	395421	100.19	2266544	100.42
2	395748	100.11	2267878	100.48
3	395864	100.22	2265850	100.39
4	395660	100.17	2266982	100.44
5	395508	100.13	2268740	100.52
6	395285	100.07	2267108	100.45
Mean	395581	100.15	2267183	100.45

Discussion: Mean % assay of Pioglitazone and Glimperide 100.15 and 100.45 respectively.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Table 12: Summary table

Parameters	Pioglitazone	Glimperide
Retention time (min)	4.713	6.691
Wave length (nm)	289	289
USP Plate count	7537	8359
System precision (% RSD)	0.042	0.057
Method precision (% RSD)	0.054	0.052
LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.070	0.096
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.212	0.293
Linearity Range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	20-80	20-80
Regression coefficient	0.9999	0.9999
Slope (m)	9884	56481
Intercept (c)	-380.46	-2387.5
Regression equation ($Y=mx+c$)	$Y=9884.3x-380.46$	$Y=56481x-2387.5$
Accuracy (% recovery)	100.16	100.29
Assay (% mean assay)	100.15	100.45
Robustness (tailing factor)		
i) Flow rate of 0.8ml/min	0.024	0.027
ii) Flow rate of 1.0ml/min	0.020	0.021
iii) Flow rate of 1.2ml/min	0.025	0.034

CONCLUSION

A simple, accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Pioglitazone

and Glimperide in Tablet dosage form. The analysis of several parameters served as the foundation for the development of an analytical

method. The absorbance for glimepiride was 270 nm and 265 nm for pioglitazone. But at 289 nm the peak was excellent. 20µl was chosen as the injection volume since it produced good peak area. ODS Inertsil C18 was chosen as the column for the study and a flow rate of 1.0ml/min was selected. Different mobile phase ratios were tried and Methanol: Acetonitrile (70:30) had well-symmetrical peaks and high resolution. The analytical method found linear between 20 and 80 ppm. The parameters like precision, robustness and ruggedness were within the limits. Thus, the developed method was sensitive, precise, accurate and can be used for routine analysis.

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